

Strategies and interventions to strengthen pharmacovigilance systems in low- and middle-income countries: a scoping review

Supplementary file 1 - Appendices

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Appendix I: Search strategy in Ovid MEDLINE

((afghanistan OR albania OR algeria OR american samoa OR angola OR "antigua and barbuda" OR antigua OR barbuda OR argentina OR armenia OR armenian OR aruba OR azerbaijan OR bahrain OR bangladesh OR barbados OR republic of belarus OR belarus OR byelarus OR belorussia OR byelorussian OR belize OR british honduras OR benin OR dahomey OR bhutan OR bolivia OR "bosnia and herzegovina" OR bosnia OR herzegovina OR botswana OR bechuanaland OR brazil OR brasil OR bulgaria OR burkina faso OR burkina fasso OR upper volta OR burundi OR urundi OR cabo verde OR cape verde OR cambodia OR kampuchea OR khmer republic OR cameroon OR cameron OR cameroun OR central african republic OR ubangi shari OR chad OR chile OR china OR colombia OR comoros OR comoro islands OR iles comores OR mayotte OR democratic republic of the congo OR democratic republic congo OR congo OR zaire OR costa rica OR "cote d'ivoire" OR "cote d' ivoire" OR cote divoire OR cote d ivoire OR ivory coast OR croatia OR cuba OR cyprus OR czech republic OR czechoslovakia OR djibouti OR french somaliland OR dominica OR dominican republic OR ecuador OR egypt OR united arab republic OR el salvador OR equatorial guinea OR spanish guinea OR eritrea OR estonia OR eswatini OR swaziland OR ethiopia OR fiji OR gabon OR gabonese republic OR gambia OR "georgia (republic)" OR georgian OR ghana OR gold coast OR gibraltar OR greece OR grenada OR guam OR guatemala OR guinea OR guinea bissau OR guyana OR british guiana OR haiti OR hispaniola OR honduras OR hungary OR india OR indonesia OR timor OR iran OR iraq OR isle of man OR jamaica OR jordan OR kazakhstan OR kazakh OR kenya OR "democratic people's republic of korea" OR republic of korea OR north korea OR south korea OR korea OR kosovo OR kyrgyzstan OR kirghizia OR kirgizstan OR kyrgyz republic OR kirghiz OR laos OR lao pdr OR "lao people's democratic republic" OR latvia OR lebanon OR lebanese republic OR lesotho OR basutoland OR liberia OR libya OR libyan arab jamahiriya OR lithuania OR macau OR macao OR republic of north macedonia OR macedonia OR madagascar OR malagasy republic OR malawi OR nyasaland OR malaysia OR malay federation OR malaya federation OR maldives OR indian ocean islands OR indian ocean OR mali OR malta OR micronesia OR federated states of micronesia OR kiribati OR marshall islands OR nauru OR northern mariana islands OR palau OR tuvalu OR mauritania OR mauritius OR mexico OR moldova OR moldovian OR mongolia OR montenegro OR morocco OR ifni OR mozambique OR portuguese east africa OR myanmar OR burma OR namibia OR nepal OR netherlands antilles OR nicaragua OR niger OR nigeria OR oman OR muscat OR pakistan OR panama OR papua new guinea OR new guinea OR paraguay OR peru OR philippines OR philipines OR phillipines OR philippines OR poland OR "polish people's republic" OR portugal OR portuguese republic OR puerto rico OR romania OR russia OR russian federation OR ussr OR soviet union OR union of soviet socialist republics OR rwanda OR ruanda OR samoa OR pacific islands OR polynesia OR samoan islands OR navigator island OR navigator islands OR "sao tome and principe" OR saudi arabia OR senegal OR serbia OR seychelles OR sierra leone OR slovakia OR slovak republic OR slovenia OR melanesia OR solomon island OR solomon islands OR norfolk island OR norfolk islands OR somalia OR south africa OR south sudan OR sri lanka OR ceylon OR "saint kitts and nevis" OR "st. kitts and nevis" OR saint lucia OR "st. lucia" OR "saint vincent and the grenadines" OR saint vincent OR "st. vincent" OR grenadines OR sudan OR suriname OR surinam OR dutch guiana OR netherlands guiana OR syria OR syrian arab republic OR tajikistan OR tadjikistan OR tadhikistan OR tadhik OR tanzania OR tanganyika OR thailand OR siam OR timor leste OR east timor OR togo OR togolese republic OR tonga OR "trinidad and tobago" OR trinidad OR tobago OR tunisia OR turkey OR turkmenistan OR turkmen OR uganda OR ukraine OR uruguay OR uzbekistan OR uzbek OR vanuatu OR new hebrides OR venezuela OR vietnam OR viet nam OR middle east OR

montenegrin? OR moroccan? OR mozambican? OR burmese OR myanma OR namibian? OR nauruan? OR nepali OR nepalese OR netherlands antillean? OR nicaraguan? OR nigerien? OR nigerian? OR northern mariana islander? OR mariana? OR omani? OR pakistani? OR palauan? OR panamanian? OR papua new guinean? OR paraguayan? OR peruvian? OR philippine? OR philipine? OR phillipine? OR phillippine? OR filipino? OR filipina? OR polish OR pole OR poles OR portuguese OR puerto rican? OR romanian? OR russian? OR soviet people OR soviet population OR rwandan? OR rwandese OR ruandan? OR ruandese OR samoan? OR sao tomean? OR santomean? OR saudi arabian? OR saudi? OR senegalese OR serbian? OR montenegrin? OR seychellois OR seychelloise? OR sierra leonean? OR slovak? OR slovene? OR solomon islander? OR somali? OR south african? OR south sudanese OR sri lankan? OR ceylonese OR kittitian? OR nevisian? OR saint lucian? OR vincentian? OR sudanese OR surinamese? OR syrian? OR tajik? OR tajikistani? OR tanzanian? OR tanganyikan? OR thai OR timorese? OR togolese OR tongan? OR trinidadian? OR tobagonian? OR tunisian? OR turk? OR turkish OR turkmen? OR tuvaluan? OR ugandan? OR ukrainian? OR uruguayan? OR uzbek? OR vanuatu* OR venezuelan? OR vietnamese OR yemeni? OR yemenite? OR yemenese OR yugoslav? OR yugoslavian? OR zambian? OR zimbabwean?.ti,ab,sh,kf.)

AND (((exp adverse drug reaction reporting systems/ OR exp pharmacovigilance/ OR exp product surveillance, postmarketing/ OR ((exp drug-related side effects and adverse reactions/ OR exp adverse effects/ OR exp adverse drug event/) AND (report*.ti,ab. OR system.ti,ab. OR systems*.ti,ab. OR monitor*.ti,ab. OR surveill*.ti,ab.))) AND (increas*.ti,ab. OR improv*.ti,ab. OR enhanc*.ti,ab. OR promot*.ti,ab. OR education.ti,ab. OR strengthen*.ti,ab. OR capacity building.ti,ab. OR building capacity.ti,ab. OR implement*.ti,ab. OR operat*.ti,ab. OR develop*.ti,ab. OR building*.ti,ab.)) OR ((pharmacovigilance.ti,ab. OR adverse drug reaction reporting systems.ti,ab. OR pharmacovigilance program*.ti,ab. OR pharmacovigilance activit*.ti,ab. OR adverse drug event surveillance system.ti,ab. OR adverse event monitoring.ti,ab. OR vaccine safety system*.ti,ab. OR drug safety.ti,ab. OR vaccine safety.ti,ab. OR safety surveillance .ti,ab. OR pharmacogovernance.ti,ab. OR ((adverse event*.ti,ab. OR adverse drug reaction*.ti,ab. OR side effect*.ti,ab. OR adverse effect*.ti,ab. OR adverse reaction*.ti,ab. OR undesirable event*.ti,ab. OR adverse event following immunization.ti,ab.)) ADJ2 (report*.ti,ab. OR system.ti,ab. OR systems*.ti,ab. OR monitor*.ti,ab. OR surveill*.ti,ab.))) ADJ3 (increas*.ti,ab. OR improv*.ti,ab. OR enhanc*.ti,ab. OR promot*.ti,ab. OR education.ti,ab. OR strengthen*.ti,ab. OR capacity building.ti,ab. OR building capacity.ti,ab. OR implement*.ti,ab. OR operat*.ti,ab. OR develop*.ti,ab. OR building*.ti,ab.)))

Appendix II: Sources of grey literature search

Search terms use: *pharmacovigilance strategy, pharmacovigilance strengthening*

Source	Organisation	Website
Brazil	Anvisa	https://www.gov.br/anvisa/pt-br
Burkina Faso	Direction Générale de la Pharmacie, du Médicament et des Laboratoires Direction	https://www.servicepublic.gov.bf/contact/direction-generale-de-la-pharmacie-du-medicament-et-des-laboratoires
Cameroon	Direction de la Pharmacie du Médicament et des Laboratoires (DPML)	https://dpml.cm/index.php/en/home-en#
Chile	ISP	https://www.ispch.gob.cl/
Côte d'Ivoire	Autorité Ivoirienne de Régulation Pharmaceutique	AIRP Au cœur de l'activité pharmaceutique https://www.airp.ci/frGahana
Ghana	Food and Drugs Authority	http://www.fdaghana.gov.gh/
India	Central Drugs Standard Control Organization	https://cdsco.gov.in/opencms/opencms/en/PvPI/
Kazakhstan	Ministry of Healthcare of the Republic of Kazakhstan	https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/dsm?lang=en
Kenya	Pharmacy and Poisons Board	https://web.pharmacyboardkenya.org/pharmacovigilance/mala
Malawi	Pharmacy and Medicines Regulatory Authority (PMRA)	https://pmra.mw/
Morocco	Centre Anti Poison et PV du Maroc	http://www.capm-sante.ma/pv-pharmacovigilance
Namibia	Namibia Medicines Regulatory Council	https://nmrc.gov.na/
Nigeria	National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control	https://www.nafdac.gov.ng/
Senegal	La Direction de la Pharmacie et du Médicament	https://www.sante.gouv.sn/les-directions/la-direction-de-la-pharmacie-et-du-m%C3%A9dicament
Serbia	Medicines and Medical Devices Agency of Serbia (ALIMS)	https://www.alims.gov.rs/english/pharmacovigilance/
South Africa	South African Health Products Regulatory Authority (SAHPRA) Uganda FDA	https://www.sahpra.org.za/
Tanzania	Tanzania Medicines and Medical Devices Authority (TMDA)	https://www.tmda.go.tz/
Uganda	National Drug Authority	https://www.nda.or.ug/
	Uppsala Monitoring Centre (UMC)	https://who-umc.org/

	East African Community	https://www.eac.int/medicines-regulatory-guidelines
	Tropical Disease Research	https://tdr.who.int/
	Pharmacovigilance Africa (PAVIA)	https://pavia-africa.net/
	World Health Organisation	http://www.who.int/
	Systems for Improved Access to Pharmaceuticals and Services (SIAPS) Program	https://siapsprogram.org/
	WHO Regional Office for Africa	https://www.afro.who.int/
	WHO Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean	https://www.emro.who.int/index.html
	WHO Regional Office for Southeast Asia	https://www.who.int/southeastasia
	Management Sciences for Health (MSH)	https://msh.org/
	USAID	https://www.usaid.gov/
	Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation	https://www.gatesfoundation.org/
	The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)	https://www.cdc.gov/
	African Collaborating Centre For Pharmacovigilance & Surveillance (ACC)	https://www.acc-afro.org/mission.php https://www.acc-afro.org/

Appendix III: Data extraction instrument

Author/ Country	Nature of interventions	Description of interventions	Results / Outcomes	Challenges encountered	Lessons learnt and recommendations
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Appendix IV: Articles excluded on full text

1. Duplicates not initially identified (n=2)	
1	Bomene DN, Lula Y, Ntamabyaliro N, et al. Development of Pharmacovigilance System in a Resource-Limited Country, the Experience of the Democratic Republic of Congo. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2018;41(11):1120.
2	Sturkenboom M, Perez-Vilar S, Weibel D, et al. Building capacity for active surveillance of vaccine adverse events in low and middle-income countries. <i>Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf.</i> 2017;26:241-2.
2. Global recommendations (n=3)	
3	Graham JE, Borda-Rodriguez A, Huzair F, et al. Capacity for a global vaccine safety system: the perspective of national regulatory authorities. <i>Vaccine.</i> 2012;30(33):4953-9.
4	Letourneau M, Wells G, Walop W, et al. Improving global monitoring of vaccine safety: a survey of national centres participating in the WHO Programme for International Drug Monitoring. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2008;31(5):389-98.
5	Pal SN, Olsson S, Brown EG. The monitoring medicines project: a multinational pharmacovigilance and public health project. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2015;38(4):319-28.
3. Survey / systematic review (n=4)	
6	Agoro OO, Kibira SW, Freeman JV, et al. Barriers to the success of an electronic pharmacovigilance reporting system in Kenya: an evaluation three years post implementation. <i>J Am Med Inform Assoc.</i> 2018;25(6):627-34.
7	Paudyal V, Al-Hamid A, Bowen M, et al. Interventions to improve spontaneous adverse drug reaction reporting by healthcare professionals and patients: systematic review and meta-analysis. <i>Expert Opin Drug Saf.</i> 2020;19(9):1173-91.
8	Suku CK, Hill G, Sabblah G, et al. Experiences and Lessons From Implementing Cohort Event Monitoring Programmes for Antimalarials in Four African Countries: Results of a Questionnaire-Based Survey. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2015;38(11):1115-26.
9	Zhao Y, Wang T, Li G, et al. Pharmacovigilance in China: development and challenges. <i>Int J Clin Pharm.</i> 2018;40(4):823-31.
4. Developed country (n=5)	
10	Baek HJ, Cho YS, Kim KS, et al. Multidisciplinary approach to improve spontaneous ADR reporting in the pediatric outpatient setting: a single-institute experience in Korea. <i>Springerplus.</i> 2016;5(1):1435.
11	Black S, Mulholland K, Halsey NA. Developing sustainable funding for vaccine safety infrastructure. <i>Vaccine.</i> 2010;28(5):1133-4.
12	Cheema E, Almuallem AA, Basudan AT, et al. Assessing the impact of structured education on the knowledge of hospital pharmacists about adverse drug reactions and reporting methods in Saudi Arabia: an open-label randomised controlled trial. <i>Drugs Ther Perspect.</i> 2019;35(6):296-300.
13	Kang DY, Ahn KM, Kang HR, et al. Past, present, and future of pharmacovigilance in Korea. <i>Asia Pac Allergy.</i> 2017;7(3):173-8.
14	Tabali M, Jeschke E, Bockelbrink A, et al. Educational intervention to improve physician reporting of adverse drug reactions (ADRs) in a primary care setting in complementary and alternative medicine. <i>BMC Public Health.</i> 2009;9:11.

5. Outcomes of interest not clearly defined (n=7)	
15	AbuAlRub RF, Al-Akour NA, Alatari NH. Perceptions of reporting practices and barriers to reporting incidents among registered nurses and physicians in accredited and nonaccredited Jordanian hospitals. <i>J Clin Nurs</i> . 2015;24(19-20):2973-82.
16	Ceballos M, Salazar-Ospina A, Sabater-Hernandez D, et al. Evaluation of the effects of a drug with fiscalized substance dispensation, health education, and pharmacovigilance continuing education program in Colombia drugstores and drugstores/pharmacies: study protocol of a multicenter, cluster-randomized controlled trial. <i>Trials</i> . 2020;21(1):545.
17	Chahal HS, Kashfipour F, Susko M, et al. Establishing a regulatory value chain model: An innovative approach to strengthening medicines regulatory systems in resource-constrained settings. <i>Am J Public Health</i> . 2016;39(5):299-305.
18	Lahariya C, Paruthi R, Bhattacharya M. How a New Health Intervention Affects the Health Systems? Learnings from Pentavalent Vaccine Introduction in India. <i>Indian J Pediatr</i> . 2016;83(4):294-9.
19	Patel H, Gurumurthy P. Improving medication safety in oncology care: impact of clinical pharmacy interventions on optimizing patient safety. <i>Int J Clin Pharm</i> . 2019;41(4):981-92.
20	Preston C, Valdez ML, Bond K. Strengthening Medical Product Regulation in Low- and Middle-Income Countries. <i>PLoS Med</i> . 2012;9(10).
21	Shankar PR, Humagain B, Piryani RM, et al. Establishing and strengthening a medicine and therapeutics committee in a medical college in Nepal: initial experiences. <i>Pharm World Sci</i> . 2009;31(2):241-5.
6. PV system assessment (n=7)	
22	Alshammari TM, Alenzi KA, Ata SI. National pharmacovigilance programs in Arab countries: A quantitative assessment study. <i>Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf</i> . 2020;29(9):1001-10.
23	Alshammari TM, Mendi N, Alenzi KA, et al. Pharmacovigilance Systems in Arab Countries: Overview of 22 Arab Countries. <i>Drug Saf</i> . 2019;42(7):849-68.
24	Barry A, Olsson S, Minzi O, et al. Comparative assessment of the national pharmacovigilance systems in East Africa: Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda and Tanzania. <i>Drug Saf</i> . 2020:1-12.
25	Kabore L, Millet P, Fofana S, et al. Pharmacovigilance systems in developing countries: an evaluative case study in Burkina Faso. <i>Drug Saf</i> . 2013;36(5):349-58.
26	Kaewpanukrunsi W, Anantachoti P. Performance assessment of the Thai National Center for Pharmacovigilance. <i>Int J Risk Saf Med</i> . 2015;27(4):225-37.
27	Olsson S, Pal SN, Stergachis A, et al. Pharmacovigilance activities in 55 low- and middle-income countries: a questionnaire-based analysis. <i>Drug Saf</i> . 2010;33(8):689-703.
28	Opadeyi AO, Fourrier-Reglat A, Isah AO. Assessment of the state of pharmacovigilance in the South-South zone of Nigeria using WHO pharmacovigilance indicators. <i>BMC Pharmacol Toxicol</i> . 2018;19(1):27.
7. Articles in other languages (n=8)	
29	Cai T, Zhan SY. Develop the active surveillance system for vaccine safety in China. <i>Chi J Prev Med</i> . 2019;53(7):664.
30	Cao X, Tang L, Cai Z. Effects of clinical pharmacist intervention on the quality monitoring of adverse drug reactions. [Chinese]. <i>Pharm Care Res</i> . 2015;15(3):221-3.

31	Koryanova KN, Matveev AV, Egorova EA, et al. Features of International and Regional Pharmacovigilance Systems. <i>Regionologiya-Regionology- Russ J Reg Stud.</i> 2020;28(3):571-97.
32	Mira J.J. CM, Montserrat D., Rodriguez J., Santacruz J., . Key elements in implementing adverse event notification systems in Latin American hospitals. <i>Rev Panam Salud Publica.</i> 2013;33(1).
33	Pepe V. L. E. aNHMD. National Pharmacovigilance Systems in Brazil and Portugal: similarities, differences, and challenges. <i>Cad Saude Publica.</i> 2020;36(7).
34	Sánchez I, Amador C, Plaza JC, et al. Assessment of an active pharmacovigilance system carried out by a pharmacist. <i>Rev Med Chil.</i> 2014;142(8):998-1005.
35	Soyalan M, Demirdamar R, Toklu HZ, et al. National pharmacovigilance system and current practice in the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus. <i>Marmara Pharm J.</i> 2012;16(3):159-63.
36	Trujillo JC, De Guzman MA. Pharmacovigilance: "Vigilantia initiative". <i>Pharm Policy Law.</i> 2016;18(1-4):157-62.
8. Full texts not found (n=19)	
37	Amarnath S, Sharma A, Jaikumar S, et al. Impact of an educational intervention on the awareness of pharmacovigilance among pharmacy and nursing students in Puducherry. <i>Res J Pharm Biol Chem Sci.</i> 2014;5(2):1130-6.
38	Bao J. Strengthening HIV Pharmacovigilance in China. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2018;41(11):1115.
39	Caro-Rojas A. How the Colombian Pharmacovigilance Association Join the Stakeholders in Pharmacovigilance, and Promote the Best Practices in Latam? <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2018;41(11):1114.
40	Copucho HC, Reis LV, Siquoira SM, et al. Strategies Impact to Increase the Reporting of Pharmacovigilance in a Brazilian University Hospital. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2008;31(10): 953.
41	Dodoo ANO, Marfo FP. Effect of an educational intervention on improving drug safety awareness amongst sellers of non-prescription medicines in a developing country. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2005;28(10):947-947.
42	Gilani Z, Koech DC, Mecca L, et al. Strengthening the vaccine safety system in Kenya: assessment of best practices for vaccine safety among healthcare workers in Kenya. <i>Am J Trop Med Hyg.</i> 2019;101:428.
43	Gossell-Williams M, Paul T. Introducing medical students to pharmacovigilance through a Basic Research Skills Special Study Module. <i>Int J Risk Saf Med.</i> 2020;31(2):81-7.
44	Gupta YK. Ensuring patient safety - launching the new pharmacovigilance programme of India. <i>Pharma Times.</i> 2010;42(8):21-6.
45	Jamekornkul C, Suwannakaesawong W, Uerchaikul C, et al. Development of Pharmacovigilance Networking System in Thailand. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2012;35(10):935.
46	Ndiaye Y. Community based pharmacovigilance, a way forward for strengthening the pharmacovigilance system in African underserved areas: experience in Saraya health district in rural Senegal. <i>Am J Trop Med Hyg.</i> 2010;83(5):77.
47	Nyakiba JO, McMillan M, Kenyatta G. Reporting and documentation of adverse drug reactions by health care professionals at a Kenyan public hospital: A best practice implementation project. <i>JB I Database Syst Rev Implement.</i> 2014;12(7):521-33.
48	Okalebo FA, Oluka MN, Guantai AN. Learning by Doing: Implementation of Pharmacovigilance in the Clinical Setting in a National Referral Hospital in Kenya. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2018;41(11):1109-10.

49	Osakwe AI, Elemuwa UG, Akinola BO, et al. Strengthening Pharmacovigilance System Through Leveraging Resources from Public Health Programmes in Nigeria. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2011;34(10):930-1.
50	Ramirez VH. Efforts Made by the University in Costa Rica to Promote Pharmacovigilance. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2018;41(11):1114.
51	Sakin SA, Hossain AM, Mahmud SH, et al. Effect of Educational Intervention on Perception of Adverse Drug Reaction Reporting Among Medical Practitioners. <i>Mymensingh Medical Journal: MMJ.</i> 2020;29(2):399-404.
52	Thurin N, Puello A, Haramburu F. Pharmacovigilance System Implementation in a Middle-Income Country: the Case of the Dominican Republic. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2015;38(10):1032.
53	Wong A, Sandron CA. Increasing drug safety and ADR reporting in Latin America: The crucial role of poison information centres. <i>Toxicology.</i> 2001;164(1-3):8-9.
54	Yavo JC, Assi SB, Kamagate M, et al. Implementation of a national pharmacovigilance system and drug risk management in a French-speaking African country, Cote d'Ivoire: review and Prospects. <i>Fundam Clin Pharmacol.</i> 2018;32:62.
55	Yousef T, Abbas A, Ali T, et al. The Experience of using Khartoum Medicines Information Center (Khmic) as a Focal Point to Enhance Pharmacovigilance In Sudan. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2018;41(11):1187-8.
9. No interventions/strategy described (n=40)	
56	Abiri OT, Johnson WC. Pharmacovigilance systems in resource-limited settings: an evaluative case study of Sierra Leone. <i>J Pharm Policy Pract.</i> 2019;12(1):13.
57	Adenuga BA, Kibuule D, Rennie TW. Optimizing spontaneous adverse drug reaction reporting in public healthcare setting in Namibia. <i>Basic Clin Pharmacol Toxicol.</i> 2020;126(3):247-53.
58	Ahuja V, Sharma V. Training in Post-authorization Pharmacovigilance. <i>Perspect Clin Res.</i> 2010;1(2):70-5.
59	Amarasinghe A, Black S, Bonhoeffer J, et al. Effective vaccine safety systems in all countries: a challenge for more equitable access to immunization. <i>Vaccine.</i> 2013;31 Suppl 2:B108-14.
60	Andrade PHS, de Almeida ACB, Dos Santos AKS, et al. Challenges to the consolidation of pharmacovigilance practices in Brazil: limitations of the hospital pharmacist. <i>Ther Adv Drug Saf.</i> 2020;11:2042098620933748.
61	Apte AA. Reporting of adverse events for marketed drugs: Need for strengthening safety database. <i>Perspect Clin Res.</i> 2016;7(3):111-4.
62	Babigumira JB, Stergachis A, Choi HL, et al. A framework for assessing the economic value of pharmacovigilance in low- and middle-income countries. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2014;37(3):127-34.
63	Black S, Zuber PLF. Global trends and challenges in vaccine safety. <i>Ped Health.</i> 2009;3(4):329-35.
64	Bonhoeffer J, Kohl K, Chen R, et al. The Brighton Collaboration - Enhancing vaccine safety. <i>Vaccine.</i> 2004;22(15-16):2046.
65	Chen RT, Shimabukuro TT, Martin DB, et al. Enhancing Vaccine Safety Capacity Globally: A Lifecycle Perspective. <i>Am J Prev Med.</i> 2015;49(6 Suppl 4):S364-76.
66	Dylan Fernandes S, Anoop NV, Castelino LJ, et al. A national approach to pharmacovigilance: The case of India as a growing hub of global clinical trials. <i>Res Social Adm Pharm.</i> 2019;15(1):109-13.
67	Elshafie S, Zaghoul I, Roberti AM. Pharmacovigilance in developing countries (part I): importance and challenges. <i>Int J Clin Pharm.</i> 2018;40(4):758-63.

68	Guillard-Maure C, Elango V, Black S, et al. Operational lessons learned in conducting a multi-country collaboration for vaccine safety signal verification and hypothesis testing: The global vaccine safety multi country collaboration initiative. <i>Vaccine</i> . 2018;36(3):355-62.
69	Hamid AA, Mohamed Ibrahim MI. A Systematic Scoping Review of the State of Pharmacovigilance and Governance in the MENA Region: Challenges and Opportunities. <i>Pharmaceut Med</i> . 2017;31(6):437-54.
70	Hartigan-Go K, Roces MC, Habacon CA, et al. Developing an immunization safety surveillance system in the Philippines. <i>Bull World Health Organ</i> . 2000;78(9):1166.
71	Helali AM, Iqbal MJ, Islam MZ, et al. The evolving role of pharmacovigilance and drug safety: The way forward for Bangladesh. <i>Int J Pharm Res</i> . 2014;6(4):31-7.
72	Hussain R, Hassali MA. Current status and future prospects of pharmacovigilance in Pakistan. <i>J Pharm Policy Pract</i> . 2019;12:14.
73	Kabore L, Yameogo TM, Sombie I, et al. Plaidoyer pour un renforcement du système de pharmacovigilance au Burkina Faso. <i>Santé Publique</i> . 2017;29(6):921-5.
74	Khan Z, Karatas Y, Rahman H. Adverse drug reactions reporting in Turkey and barriers: an urgent need for pharmacovigilance education. <i>Ther Adv Drug Saf</i> . 2020;11:2042098620922483.
75	Kochhar S, Edwards KM, Ropero Alvarez AM, et al. Introduction of new vaccines for immunization in pregnancy - Programmatic, regulatory, safety and ethical considerations. <i>Vaccine</i> . 2019;37(25):3267-77.
76	Kucuku M. Role of pharmacovigilance on vaccines control. <i>J Rural Med</i> . 2012;7(1):42-5.
77	Lokesh RV, Adusumilli PK, Shashi B, et al. Integration of pharmacy education and pharmacovigilance: scope and challenges in india. <i>Indian J Pharm Educ Res</i> . 2019;53(2):202-7.
78	Mahajan V, Saini SS. Improving AEFI surveillance in India. <i>Indian Pediatr</i> . 2014;51(3):233.
79	Mandal SC, Mandal M. Evolution of pharmacovigilance programme: Present status in India. <i>Pharma Times</i> . 2017;49(5):31-6.
80	Mehta U, Durrheim D, Mabuza A, et al. Malaria pharmacovigilance in Africa: lessons from a pilot project in Mpumalanga Province, South Africa. <i>Drug Saf</i> . 2007;30(10):899-910.
81	Meyer JC, Schellack N, Stokes J, et al. Ongoing initiatives to improve the quality and efficiency of medicine use within the public healthcare system in South Africa; a preliminary study. <i>Front Pharmacol</i> . 2017;8:751.
82	Moscou K, Kohler JC. Matching safety to access: global actors and pharmacogovernance in Kenya- a case study. <i>Glob Health</i> . 2017;13(1):20.
83	Mulchandani R, Kakkar AK. Reporting of adverse drug reactions in India: A review of the current scenario, obstacles and possible solutions. <i>Int J Risk Saf Med</i> . 2019;30(1):33-44.
84	Oliveira PMN, Lignani LK, Conceicao DAD, et al. Surveillance of adverse events following immunization in the late 2010s: an overview of the importance, tools, and challenges. <i>Cad Saude Publica</i> . 2020;36(Suppl 2):e00182019.
85	Olowofela A, Fourrier-Reglat A, Isah AO. Pharmacovigilance in Nigeria: An Overview. <i>Pharmaceut Med</i> . 2016;30(2):87-94.
86	Olsson S, Pal SN, Stergachis A, et al. Pharmacovigilance activities in 55 low- and middle-income countries: a questionnaire-based analysis. <i>Drug Saf</i> . 2010;33(8):689-703.

87	Palaian S, Mohamed Ibrahim MI, Mishra P. Development of pharmacovigilance training module for community pharmacists in Nepal: A focus group study. <i>Arch Pharm Pract.</i> 2016;7(4):130-5.
88	Perez-Vilar S, Weibel D, Sturkenboom M, et al. Enhancing global vaccine pharmacovigilance: Proof-of-concept study on aseptic meningitis and immune thrombocytopenic purpura following measles-mumps containing vaccination. <i>Vaccine.</i> 2018;36(3):347-54.
89	Prakongsai N, Pongchaidecha M. Using collaborative program between pharmacists and nurses to improve spontaneous adverse drug reaction reporting system in Thailand. <i>Value Health.</i> 2010;13(7):A537.
90	Rachlis B, Karwa R, Chema C, et al. Targeted Spontaneous Reporting: Assessing Opportunities to Conduct Routine Pharmacovigilance for Antiretroviral Treatment on an International Scale. <i>Drug Saf.</i> 2016;39(10):959-76.
91	Shukla S, Gupta M, Pandit S, et al. Implementation of adverse event reporting for medical devices, India. <i>Bull World Health Organ.</i> 2020;98(3):206-11.
92	Simha H, Marisarla S, Mujeebuddin CS. Pharmacovigilance system in India. <i>Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res.</i> 2020;63(1):73-80.
93	Stefanov O, Sharayeva M, Jajtchenja V. Development of pharmacovigilance system in Ukraine: first results. <i>Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf.</i> 2004;13(3):197-9.
94	Varallo FR, Forgerini M, Herdeiro MT, et al. Harmonization of Pharmacovigilance Regulation in Brazil: Opportunities to Improve Risk Communication. <i>Clin Ther.</i> 2019;41(3):598-603.
95	Zhou Y, Miller V, Hogan M, et al. An overview of adverse drug reaction monitoring in China. <i>Int J Pharm Med.</i> 2006;20(2):79-85.

Appendix V: Regions and countries

Region ¹	Number of Publications	Countries
East Asia Pacific region	9	China (3), Philippines (2), Malaysia (2), Vietnam (2)
Europe and Central Asia	1	Kazakhstan (1)
Latin America and the Caribbean	6	Bolivia (1), Brazil (2), Mexico (2), Multi-country (1) (Argentina, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Honduras, Peru, and Uruguay)
Middle East and North Africa	5	Egypt (1), Iran (1), Jordan (1), Lebanon (1), Morocco (1)
South Asia	17	India (12), Nepal (3), Multi-country (2) : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Indonesia, Maldives, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Timor-Leste and Vietnam • Bangladesh, Bhutan, DRP Korea, India, Indonesia, Maldives, Myanmar, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Thailand and Timor Este
Sub-Saharan Africa	28	Burkina Faso (1), Cameroon (2), Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) (1), Ethiopia (1), Malawi (2), Mozambique (2), Namibia (1), Nigeria (4), Rwanda (1), Senegal (1), South Africa (4), Sudan (1), Swaziland (2), Tanzania (2), Uganda (1) Multi-country (2): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ghana, Kenya and Malawi • Benin, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Chad, Ethiopia, Ghana, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sudan, and The Gambia
Global/LMIC	4	Global recommendations
Total	70	

¹ According to World Bank region classification (1)

Appendix VI: Nature of interventions and outcomes

Author Year Country	Nature of interventions	Objectives	Description of interventions	Outcome/effectiveness of interventions	Challenges encountered	Lessons learnt and recommendations
1. Interventions aimed at increasing PV knowledge and AE or ADR reporting						
1.1. Educational interventions (21)						
1. Elkalmi et al., (2) 2011 Malaysia	Educational	To assess the knowledge and perception of community pharmacists in Malaysia towards the reporting of ADRs and to evaluate the effectiveness of an educational program to improve knowledge on ADR reporting.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of an educational program on PV and ADR reporting for community pharmacists 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant increase in mean PV knowledge scores and ADR reporting compared to the baseline 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low participation rate 	None reported
2. Khalili (3), 2012 Iran	Educational	Evaluation of clinical pharmacists' interventions in improvement of knowledge, attitude and perception about ADRs in a teaching hospital.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training workshops 3 hour weekly for four weeks • Continuous sensitization on ADRs every other day for 1 month • Practice on completing yellow card 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement in recognition and reporting of ADRs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unawareness of the existence of a national ADR reporting system • Under-reporting due to insufficient information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health systems must have PV training and guidance on how to report ADRs
3. Osakwe et al., (4), 2013 Nigeria	Educational	To determine the knowledge and practice of PV amongst HCP in Nigeria and the impact of previous training in PV on their knowledge and practice.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Email distribution of quarterly PV newsletters • Formal face-to face training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respondent's knowledge and practice of PV was generally inadequate despite the fact that about a third were trained on PV 	None reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovations in PV training methods are necessary for better impact
4. Sanghavi et al., (5), 2013 India	Educational	To evaluate the baseline knowledge, attitude and practice of the doctors on ADR monitoring and PV, to identify reasons for under reporting and plan an effective intervention to inculcate ADR reporting in clinical practice.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 45 minutes lecture on PV 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intervention improved the knowledge, attitude and awareness of the ADR reporting system. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Under reporting due to lack of time and poor understanding of ADR reporting system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training could be improved with supportive tools such as job aids
5. Bisht et al., (6), 2014 India	Educational	To assess the level of knowledge, attitude, and the practices of PV among doctors attending educational training for improving awareness of PV.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A lecture to increase awareness of ongoing PV program in the institute 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant increase in the knowledge and awareness of PV though no major difference in practice 	None reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous education and others strategies needed to improve the awareness and reporting of ADRs

6. MacDonald et al., (7), 2015 Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Indonesia, Maldives, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Timor-Leste Vietnam	Educational	Enhance regional capacity to evaluate investigated AEFI and carry out causality assessment of serious AEFI previously assessed by country committees.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three-day 10 country workshop to strengthen causality assessment • Group work to review and assess cases AEFI • Interactive discussions on to improve AEFI investigation and causality assessment in the region 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs identification and improvement in AEFI investigations and causality 	None reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LMICs need WHO AEFI tools adapted to better fit LMIC • Importance of data sharing and networking
7. Alraie et al., (8), 2016 Egypt	Educational	To assess the impact of PV awareness workshop on knowledge of hospital pharmacists; and to identify the main factors and barriers that influence ADR reporting.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three-day PV awareness workshop • A follow-up phone call after three months to detect barriers encountered • Monitoring and analysis of ADR reports for six months 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased knowledge and awareness after intervention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reporting hindered by lack of time and administrative barriers • Inability to complete patient details 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited number ADR reports in the 6 months follow-up period, indicating that education alone does not suffice to promote reporting
8. Morales Rio et al., (9), 2016 Mexico	Educational	Assess the effectiveness of a comprehensive intervention coordinated by a pharmacist.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1h group informative talk on PV • Reminders to medical staff during medical visits or retrospective review of medical records • Feedback to medical staff Improve accessibility to the ADR reporting forms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seven-fold increase in ADR identification after intervention • Fourteen-fold increase in ADR reporting compared to pre-intervention • The effect on both variables was maintained 6 months after the intervention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medical records review was expensive – time and human resource-consuming • Underreporting of ADRs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pharmacists play an important role in ADR reporting
9. Jha et al., (10), 2017	Educational	To examine community pharmacists' knowledge and attitude about pharmacovigilance before and after an educational intervention.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2h Training on PV • Poster sessions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement in knowledge and attitude towards PV 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HCP lack time for ADR reporting • Lack of continuous feedback and information sharing on ADRs 	None reported
10. Varallo et al., Brazil (11), 2017 Nepal	Educational	To assess the impact of a multifaceted educational intervention on the prevalence of ADR reporting.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A lecture on PV concepts with a practical class on completing ADR reports • Distribution of educational materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 70-fold increase in the number of ADR reports during the 12 months post-intervention, though this decreased after the first 4 months • Improvement in form-completion skills PV knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV training not included in new hospital risk management and patient safety policy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of reports decreased after the first four months, suggesting the need for periodic retraining

11. Abu Farha et al., (12), 2018 Jordan	Educational	To evaluate the impact of an educational workshop on the knowledge and perception of HCP towards PV in a Jordanian tertiary teaching hospital.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1h educational workshop on PV 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement in knowledge and perception scores 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The influence on the practice of ADRs reporting was not studied 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous training and different strategies needed to encourage adherence to appropriate PV practices
12. Damdar et al., (13) 2018 India	Educational	To analyse the impact of educational intervention on the knowledge of PV.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A workshop on filling the spontaneous ADR reporting form and demonstration of WHO and Naranjo causality assessment scale 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in knowledge and awareness of PV monitoring and reporting ADRs 	None reported	None reported
13. Albadawi et al., (14), 2019 Sudan	Educational	To evaluate HCP's knowledge and attitude towards PV among health professionals in Ribat University Hospital, Sudan and to assess the impact of an intervention.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV lecture sessions • Pamphlets • Mobile phones reminders or posters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mean PV knowledge and attitude significantly improved post-intervention 	None reported	None reported
14. Bepari et al., (15), 2019 India	Educational	To evaluate the impact of a multi-faceted educational intervention on the knowledge, perception, and practice skills of PV among undergraduate pharmacy students.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lecture on PV concepts with practical lessons on completing ADR forms • Distribution of educational material to participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant improvement in the knowledge, perceptive behaviour, and practice skills scores of PV 	None reported	None reported
15. Deepalakshmi et al., (16), 2019 India	Educational	To educate and train the community pharmacists on PV and assess the knowledge, attitude and practice of ADR monitoring and implementation of ADR reporting in their practice.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distribution and filling of ADR forms • PV awareness trainings • ADR awareness posters displayed at community pharmacies • Follow-up after 6 months to assess the changes if any changes in practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of ADR monitoring services in selected community pharmacies • Significant increase in knowledge and practice of PV 	None reported	None reported
16. Gebreyohannes et al., (17), 2019 Ethiopia	Educational	Assess whether pictorial intervention would help to identify and improve ADR reporting in an ARV clinic in Northwest Ethiopia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation of a pictogram-enhanced tool to identify and report ADRs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pictorial representation resulted in only slight improvement in identification and reporting of ADRs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single centre study • Most participants were from low to middle socioeconomic class 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pictograms can be used to educate about ADRs associated with ARV
17. Zaveri et al., (18), 2019 India	Educational	Impact of educational training on knowledge, attitude, and practice of pharmacovigilance in nursing staff of tertiary care hospital.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One-hour interventional lecture on ADRs and PV in India with a practical session on how to complete an ADR reporting form 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant increase in knowledge and attitude towards PV however only 12% of participants reported an ADR 	None reported	None reported
18. Shrestha et al., (19), 2020 Nepal	Educational	The main aim of the study was to assess the impact of an education intervention on the knowledge and attitude of HCP attached to the	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2h training and interactive session on PV with distribution of posters and handouts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant increase in mean knowledge score on PV and ADR as well as attitude towards PV 	None reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration of professionals and patients could drive and inform best practices in ADR reporting

		regional PV centre in an oncology based hospital of Nepal.				
19. Siddiqui et al., (20), 2020 India	Educational	To assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice of PV and ADR reporting of HCP before and after an educational intervention.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interactive educational session • Follow-up and reminders for one month 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant improvement in overall knowledge and attitude of HCP • ADRs increased from 0 to 10 during the 1 month follow-up period 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Underreporting of ADR due to a lack of knowledge and awareness and lack of time 	None reported
20. Vo et al., (21), 2020 Vietnam	Educational	The study aimed to describe ADR reports after an educational intervention for physicians and nurses by clinical pharmacists.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training of nurses and doctors on reporting of ADRs and diagnosis, treatment, and reporting of ADRs, respectively 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant increase in the quantity (12-fold compared to pre-intervention) and quality of ADRs reported 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in reporting rate observed in the first 8 months of follow-up was not sustained 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More intensive and specific training and other measures are needed to improve under-reporting of ADRs
21. MacDonald et al., (22),2020 Bangladesh, Bhutan, DRP Korea, India, Indonesia, Maldives, Myanmar, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Thailand and Timor Este	Educational	To strengthen regional and in-country vaccine safety capacity, with a strong focus on related communication activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three-day workshop to strengthen causality assessment • Group work to review and assess cases AEFI • Interactive discussions on to improve AEFI investigation and causality assessment in the region 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compared to 2014, AEFI detection and causality assessment skills had improved 	None reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numerous recommendations for SEAR countries, WHO Southeast Asia Regional Office, and for Global Partners

1.2. Mixed interventions (11)

1. Sevene et al., (23), 2008 Mozambique	Mixed	To examine the impact of training and monitoring of HCP, making supervisory visits and the availability of telecommunication and transport facilities on the implementation of a PV system.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training workshops on PV • Implementation of a 'yellow card' system for spontaneous reporting of ADRs • District focal person designated to facilitate communication between the health staff and the PV unit • Retraining after 5 months to reinforce learnings from the first workshop 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fourteen months after the first training, 67 ADR reports involving 74 adverse events were received by the national PV unit • Increase in quality of ADR reports after refresher training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficult to sustain ADR reporting and PV systems established • Underreporting of ADRs • Reporting affected by poor transport, access to health facilities, telecommunications and malaria transmission 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV focal point was key to the success of the implementation • Continuous training, feedback and supervisory visits essential to stimulate reporting • Means of transportation and communication is essential
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2. Agu et al., (24), 2012 Nigeria	Mixed	To evaluate the change in knowledge, attitudes and practices of healthcare professionals about ADR monitoring and reporting after six months of capacity building interventions in a Nigerian tertiary hospital.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Five-day group training on PV for antiretroviral (ARV) drugs • Establishing a multidisciplinary ARV PV Committee to coordinate PV of ARV in the hospital • Regular feedback and data review • Dissemination of PV standard operating procedures and reporting forms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in mean knowledge and attitude scores at post-intervention • Increase in number of HCP reporting ADRs • 163 yellow cards were received from 49 pharmacists 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack/inadequate knowledge on ADR reporting • Unavailability of reporting forms • Ignorance of reporting procedures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HCP were more willing to practice PV following the intervention
3. Santosh et al., (25), 2013 Nepal	Mixed	To provide an overview of PV and HCP perspectives on ADR reporting in Nepal and to provide recommendations on possible ways to improve ADR reporting.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training of HCP to increase awareness and encourage reporting • Design appropriate training tools to enhance knowledge of ADR reporting among HCP • Expand the current ADR monitoring program to cover the whole country • Establish a functional PV advisory committee to take any technical decision related to ADR monitoring and ADR reports and also to establish communication strategy • Encourage universities and academic institutions to provide training on PV 	None reported	None reported	None reported
4. Ateudjieu et al., (26), 2014 Cameroon	Mixed	To assess the effect of weekly SMS and weekly supervisory visits on AEFI reporting rate during a meningitis immunization campaign conducted in Cameroon in 2012 using the meningitis A conjugate vaccine (MenAfriVac™).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A weekly SMS reminder to actively detect and report AEFI • Weekly supervision by a nurse to support with AEFI detection and reporting • No intervention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The incidence of AEFI reported per 100 health facilities per week was 20.0 in the SMS group, 40.2 in supervision group and 13.6 in the control group • Supervision led to a significant increase of AEFI reporting rate compared to SMS and control group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low completion rate of AEFI reporting forms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supervision should be included as an intrinsic part of planning AEFI surveillance during vaccination campaigns
5. Poirot et al., (27), 2016 Swaziland	Mixed	To assess the feasibility and acceptability of using a simple PV tool to collect standardized safety data in persons prescribed primaquine for the treatment of <i>P. falciparum</i> malaria.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A standardized form to support the surveillance of possible adverse events following primaquine treatment • A patient information card to enhance awareness of known 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study promoted and facilitated the capture of treatment emergent AEs after initiation of primaquine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Underreporting was higher than anticipated • No baseline assessment of symptoms in order to reduce the workload for healthcare providers • Recall bias 	None reported

			<p>adverse drug reactions of primaquine</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A database compiling recorded information, was developed and piloted. 			
6. Fang et al., (28), 2017 China	Mixed	To investigate changes in spontaneous reporting compliance and ADR patterns following adoption of a new hospital reporting system, and multiple interventions designed for its improvement use under modified drug administration guidelines.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of new guidelines on antibiotic use and ADR reporting • Financial incentives to the reporting physician and department • Training on PV and ADR reporting • Improvement of the computer system • Regular publishing of ADR information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No significant difference in reporting rates pre- and post-intervention • Significant increase in total reports • Improvements in reporting compliance • Increase in reporting of serious ADRs 	None reported	None reported
7. Chang et al., (29), 2017 China	Mixed	Assess the effectiveness of a financial intervention based on a fine and a bonus for improving spontaneous reporting of ADRs by physicians in a hospital setting.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre intervention: implantation of the ADR database • First intervention: financial incentive • Second intervention: financial incentive and strict regulations for antimicrobial agents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant increase in ADRs (29 at pre-intervention; 277 at first intervention; and 666 at second intervention period) • Increase in the quality of reports 	None reported	None reported
8. Nkonde et al., (30), 2017 South Africa	Mixed	To implement interventions to strengthen the PV surveillance system for ADR reporting at Dr. George Mukhari Academic Hospital.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrospective quantitative and qualitative review of ADR reports 9 months prior to interventions • Supportive training sessions for HCP on PV and ADR reporting • Posters about ADRs and ADR reporting procedures in hospital • Feedback on ADR reporting to HCP through newsletters and meeting • Review of ADR reports for quality and completeness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant increase in number (one compared to 14 after the interventions) and completeness of ADRs reported. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low uptake of the implemented interventions due to lack of support from hospital management • Damage to and misuse of ADR boxes placed in the wards to facilitate ADR reporting • Poor attitude toward PV and resistance to change routines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training interventions should be continuous • A coordinated approach with different stakeholders would yield better results. • PV training should be incorporated into HCP undergraduate programmes • Introducing SOPs on ADR reporting is essential
9. He et al., (31), 2018 China	Mixed	To increase the number of ADR reports and promote hospital PV through a pharmacists-led ADR management model.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening information and education in key departments • Establishing an internal hospital network direct reporting system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant increase in the quantity (177 pre-intervention vs 533 post-intervention) and quality of ADRs reported 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The model has high requirements for the professional ability of pharmacists 	None reported
10. Terblanche et al., (32), 2018	Mixed	To develop, implement and evaluate a structured pharmacist-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrospective review of ADR reports 18 months prior to the intervention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of HCP reporting any ADR significantly increased 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unspecified operation challenges 	None reported

South Africa		driven PV system for in-patient ADR reporting.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Needs analysis on structures, processes and outcomes of ADR reporting ADR Training for HCP and support staff Posters in wards and public areas to increase awareness Increase access to ADR reporting forms and creating ADR reporting WhatsApp group Supervisory visits by pharmacist Distribution of SOPs on ADR reporting Data analysis and feedback to HCP 	<p>from 12.1% to 33.8% post the interventions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reasons for not reporting ADRs decreased significantly HCP knowledge of the ADR reporting improved 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The quality of the reports was not assessed 	
11. Cortes Serra et al., (33), 2020 Bolivia	Mixed	To strengthen the Bolivian PV system, focusing on Chagas disease and Tuberculosis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design and implementation of new reporting form Specific training on drug safety monitoring and ADR reporting Three follow-up visits Evaluation of the effectiveness of interventions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No differences in reporting rates between the reporting form developed by the NRA and the new form 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of knowledge on PV and ADR reporting Insufficient training HCP possibly did not see the benefits of using the new tool Lack of internet access Long-term effect cannot be evaluated yet 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reinforcement of the Bolivian PV system should involve a long-term perspective and the engagement of national stakeholders at all levels

1.3. Mobile and electronic reporting (7)

1. Tsafack et al., (34), 2015 Cameroon	Mobile and electronic reporting	To assess the effect of telephone "beep" on community based reporting rates of AEFI during routine immunization sessions in a Cameroon Health District.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Parents of vaccinated children were randomly assigned: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) to "beep" (short phone call not picked up) the investigators team in case any medical incidence occurs within the 30 days following immunization (intervention group) ii) to return to the health facility in case any medical incidence occurs within the same period (control group) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The use of "beep" significantly increased ADR reporting rate compared to routine recommendations 20 AEFI were reported within 30 days after vaccine administration; 19 of these in the intervention group and 1 AEFI in the control group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited number of participants Selection bias - majority of participants resided in an urban zone and therefore more accustomed to the use of the telephone "beep" 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mobile phone based tools like SMS have the capacity to complement existing passive reporting systems but the implication of a cost could be a barrier to reporting
2. Ithnin et al., (35), 2017 Malaysia	Mobile and electronic reporting	To develop and assess utility of mobile apps in assisting clinical decision in ADR assessments of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of ADR causality assessment App Testing and measuring the App's usability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developed apps made available in Google Play Store 609 users across different countries downloaded the App 	None reported	None reported

		causality, severity, and preventability using validated tools.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users assessed the App's usability as acceptable 		
3. Prakash et al., (36), 2019 India	Mobile and electronic reporting	To develop an indigenous Google based Android mobile application known as “ADR PvPI” and to analyse the ADR related data reported through this mobile application on pilot basis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation an android based mobile app for ADR reporting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5500 users have downloaded the app with an average rating of 4.26 • Significant increase in frequency of ADR reporting over the past year" 	None reported	None reported
4. Kadima et al., (37), 2020 Rwanda	Mobile and electronic reporting	To explore the feasibility of outpatients to self-report ADRs using mobile phone technology and to picture such ADRs and medications received.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 80 patients educated to report ADRs using mobile phones either by accepting a call from the investigators or calling directly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compared to the previous months where no ADRs were reported, 34 patients reported an ADR 	None reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The use of a mobile phone could complement reporting of ADRs and enhance PV
5. Management Sciences for Health (38), 2020 Mozambique	Mobile and electronic reporting	To implement PViMS, a web-based PV tool for monitoring medicine safety.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three-day training on active surveillance of patients on the new dolutegravir-based ARV medicine. • Implementation of active surveillance and spontaneous reporting using PViMS 	None reported	None reported	None reported
6. Uppsala Monitoring Centre, (39), 2020 Mexico	Mobile and electronic reporting	To implement Vigiflow, the UMC-developed system for reporting ADRs in Mexico.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The implementation process included workshops on using VigiFlow and VigiLyze for PV 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopting VigiFlow, enabled COFEPRIS to carry out its essential activities dynamically, with high-quality information • Vigiflow and e-reporting have been implemented throughout the country, by all stakeholders 	None reported	None reported
7. Vogler et al., (40), 2020 Brazil	Mobile and electronic reporting	To describe steps taken by Anvisa to make Brazil compliant with international PV standards and to increase the number of ADRs collected.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VigiFlow Setup • VigiFlow Operation - eReporting module, regional centre module and MAH module • Promotion and Training of HCP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 62.6 % increase in ADRs received by Anvisa compared to the same period for the previous year 	None reported	None reported

1.4. Passive and active safety surveillance systems (6)

1. Kabanywanyi et al., (41), 2010 Tanzania	Passive and active safety surveillance systems	To identify and implement strategies that help meet safety monitoring requirements in observational study for artemether-lumefantrine administered as first-line treatment for uncomplicated malaria in rural Tanzania.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of passive and active safety surveillance systems • SMS reporting • Training of HCP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in AEs reported 	None reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMS could provide a solution to communication challenges
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2. Management Sciences for Health (42), 2015 Swaziland	Passive and active safety surveillance systems	To introduce and implement the Sentinel Site-based active Surveillance System for antiretroviral and anti-TB (SSaSSa) treatment programs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of the protocol and tools for the electronic SSASSA system - installed on 5 hospitals and one clinic • Development of a recruitment system at HIV and TB sites • Dissemination of PV data from the SSASSA system at both the national and regional levels." 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A total of 956 patients have been enrolled, and 58 adverse events have been recorded 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data collection not optimal at all facilities 	None reported
3. Bravo Alcantero et al., (43), 2018 Argentina, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Honduras, Peru, and Uruguay	Passive and active safety surveillance systems	To build capacity for active surveillance of vaccine adverse events in the Americas based on the evaluation of two well-established relationships, the risk of immune thrombocytopenic purpura and aseptic meningitis following first dose of measles, mumps and rubella vaccines.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distance learning exercise to test data collection and quality • Retrospective standardized data collection of all adverse events of special interest (AESIs) over a four-year period 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study contributed 79 AESIs to the WHO international proof-of-concept hospital-based active surveillance system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant lag times between activities • Lack of access to vaccination records for all confirmed cases in a few sentinel sites 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active safety surveillance systems may be sustainable if they are integrated into national health systems
4. Ndiaye et al., (44), 2018 Senegal	Passive and active safety surveillance systems	This study aimed to determine if AE reporting could be improved using a smartphone application provided to community health workers (CHW), or by active follow-up using a symptom card provided to caregivers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced spontaneous reporting via daily SMS reminders to HCP • Active surveillance through home visits to detect and collect AEs • Training of facility staff and CHWs on PV and reporting of ADR via smartphone application • Community sensitizations • Training on causality assessment • Operationalization of a safety database 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased incidence with enhanced reporting, and active surveillance • Improved timeliness of notifications • Despite increased surveillance, no serious adverse drug reactions were detected 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The incidence of AEs decreased in successive rounds of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involving CHWs in safety reporting, and training nurses and CHWs to report using a mobile phone application, can be used to enhance safety reporting and improve timeliness of notifications
5. Mehta et al., (45),2020 South Africa	Passive and active safety surveillance systems	Implementation of a PV strategy to pilot locally relevant surveillance methods for detecting serious ADRs and signals related to artesunate+sulfadoxine/pyrimethamine.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Home follow-up of patients by malaria control staff • Enhanced spontaneous reporting of ADRs • Active hospital surveillance for malaria-related admissions • A confidential enquiry into malaria-related deaths • Adverse events monitoring during two therapeutic efficacy studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of only very few fatal cases and ADRs through home visits, enhanced spontaneous reporting, efficacy study, and active surveillance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ADRs not reported to the malaria control programme were not identified • Inadequate follow-up • Insufficient diagnosis capacity • Inadequacy of medical records • Recall bias among the next of kin of deceased individuals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A more integrated approach to disease surveillance that could incorporate elements of PV, resistance monitoring and rumour surveillance

6. Rouamba et al., (46), 2020 Burkina Faso	Passive and active safety surveillance systems	To monitor the occurrence of AEs after the use of artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACTs), identify potential drivers of reporting suspected ADRs and monitor AEs among women who were inadvertently exposed to ACTs in the first trimester of pregnancy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passive safety surveillance • Active safety surveillance • Community sensitization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Health and Demographic Surveillance System (HDSS) platform was useful in enabling passive and active surveillance of AEs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recall bias for patient reporting • Frequent stock outs of ACT drugs • Estimation of the incidence of AEs did not systematically take into consideration anomalies in biological parameters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active surveillance through an HDSS platform seems to be an achievable approach to collect safety data in rural areas
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2. Interventions aimed at strengthening various components of the national PV system (25)

1. Adenuga et al., (47), 2020 Namibia	Mixed	To explore the challenges associated with the effective integration of PV systems in public healthcare in a developing country such as Namibia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systems-related ways of improving PV and ADR-reporting -make PV routine, implement electronic reporting • Promote advocacy and awareness of PV among HCP • Include PV into educational curriculum and continuous education for HCP • Incentivisation for PV activities including feedback to HCP and recognition of best performers • Inclusive reporting by providing user-friendly ways such as mobile phones • Stakeholder engagement 	None reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weak PV policies and structures • Limited capacity and support for implementation of PV activities • Negative attitude of healthcare workers towards PV 	None reported
2. Akel et al., (48), 2019 Lebanon	Mixed	Engage pharmacists in reporting the adverse drug reactions by creating an efficient tool for this purpose.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a Medication Safety Subcommittee • Designing reporting tools and the method of report analysis • Assessing field medication safety culture; training and continuing education on medication safety 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This was a pilot testing - the first 20 ADRs reported would enable Lebanon to become a member of WHO PIDM • Better knowledge and ADR awareness after training 	None reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study highlighted the need of educational programs to emphasize the role and responsibility of pharmacists in PV practices

3. Chakrabarty et al., (49), 2011 India	Mixed	To inform, educate, and enlighten the readers about the constitution and dynamics of a PV centre.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setting up a PV centre with adequate logistic and infrastructure • Stakeholder communication and buy-in • Develop and disseminate ADR forms and PV tools • Ensure adequately qualified and trained staff • Acquiring a PV database • Foster a reporting culture • Establish procedures for PV tasks • Ensure stable funding 	None reported	None reported	None reported
4. Diomandé et al., (50), 2015 Benin, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Chad, Ethiopia, Ghana, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sudan, and The Gambia	Mixed	Establish vaccine PV systems in several African countries for post authorisation safety surveillance of for AEFI after PsA-TT mass immunization campaigns.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Four-day training workshop • National safety Committees established and trained • National PV experts trained • Country and regional coordination teams designated and trained on their roles, and responsibilities • Active surveillance for specific AEFIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of national safety committees • Active surveillance of conditions of interest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resources allocated to AEFI monitoring decreased over time, negatively impacting data quality • Poor collaboration and coordination between NRA and EPI • Poor safety communication strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous global advocacy to mobilize more resources to build national vaccine PV systems • Coordination between the EPI and the NRA essential for planning and implementation of vaccine PV systems
5. Elshafie et al., (51), 2018 LMIC	Mixed	To propose different strategies to encourage the introduction and sustain the advancement of robust pharmacovigilance systems in developing countries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training HCP using different media and incorporation PV into educational institutions and curricula of HCP • Active public engagement in PV • Facilitate ADR reporting by simplifying the process and enabling mobile and electronic reporting • Adequate data management and communication of safety signals • Well-organized healthcare systems, with effective policies and strict drug regulations • Regulations and guidelines for industry • Curbing falsified drugs 	None reported	None reported	None reported

6. Hartigan-go, (52), 2015 Philippines	Mixed	To strengthen the national PV system by reinforcing consumer reporting.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training courses on PV • Establish a national notification system • Advocacy and awareness initiatives • Introduction of a user-friendly report form • A simple causality assessment process was designed by an advisory committee • Feedback and appreciation letters and information about the reports submitted 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Over 1600 reports from various areas of the country received since • Health advisories and warnings to the health professionals and to the public • Medical device issues led to change in government procurement sources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Underreporting of herbal medicines related ADRS 	None reported
7. Hartigan-go, (53), 2002 Philippines	Mixed	To describe the establishment of the Philippine PV system and the lessons learnt.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education forum and training workshop for consumers • Simplified online (e-ADR) notification process • Distribution of advocacy materials such as posters and training materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No dramatic increase in consumer reporting observed • Quality and completeness of reports often insufficient for causality assessment • Regulatory actions such as advisories and product confiscation 	None reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumers and patients are important allies in ensuring the safety and efficacy of medicines • Social media can be a useful tool to increase awareness and gather information about PV
8. Joshi et al., (54), 2018 India	Mixed	To describe vaccine safety and surveillance for AEFI in India.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of first operational guidelines in 2005 and revised in 2015 • Establishment of state and national AEFI committees • Appointment of four Zonal AEFI consultants • AEFI committees trained in investigation and causality assessment • Development of communication tools and guidelines • Implementation of a quality management system" 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Functional AEFI surveillance system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of the reported serious AEFI are still far less than the expected numbers • Although the AEFI committees at the district and state levels have been established, a large proportion are far from functional 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AEFI surveillance program should be ready to assume greater responsibility comprehensively respond to the community concerns and sustain public confidence in vaccines
9. Jusot et al., (55), 2020 Malawi	Mixed	To improve reporting of AEs by strengthening passive safety surveillance via PV training and mentoring of local PV stakeholders and HCP.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two-day training of EPI and NRA on PV • Abridged PV training for HCP • Regular PV mentoring on site or via phone calls • Logistic support to upgrade the national PV centre - computer system, PV database 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular PV training and mentoring of HCP were effective in enhancing passive safety surveillance in Malawi. • Significant increase of number of AEs reported 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unavailability of a safety database during the implementation period • Transmission of reports to the national PV centre 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous mentoring of HCP maintains motivation • Designating a national PV coordinator is important • Creation of partnerships and leveraging

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appointing a national PV coordinator, data manager and district PV focal points • Strengthening mechanisms for ADR reporting 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No functional national safety committee during the pilot 	opportunities is essential for synergy
10. Kalaiselvan et al., (56), 2016 India	Mixed	To describe measures taken by the National Coordination Center (NCC) for PV Programme of India (PvPI) to enhance patient safety including capacity building for monitoring, surveillance, collaboration with national health programs and other organizations to increase ADR reporting.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing a Culture of Adverse Drug Reaction Reporting • Integration of PV Programme of India and Public Health Programs (PHP) • Collaborations With Central Drugs Standard Control Organization • Education and Training on PV at Regional Training Centres • Safety communications via website, media, newsletter • Helpline Facility to Provide Assistance in Adverse Drug Reaction Reporting • Android Mobile Application for Adverse Drug Reaction Reporting • Utilization of Periodic Safety Update Reports Reporting • Availability of Medicine Side Effect Reporting Form for Consumers in Different vernacular languages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The contribution of India to the WHO global Individual Case Safety Reports (ICSRs) database is 3% • ADR reporting through PvPI improved with the measures such as education, training, and provision of technical assistance 	None reported	None reported
11. Meher, (57), 2019 India	Mixed	To describe vaccine safety and surveillance for AEFI in India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of AEFI guidelines in 2005, revised in 2010 and 2015 • AEFI committees were set up in 2008 • National AEFI Secretariat and National AEFI Technical Collaborating Centre were established for technical oversight and support • Launch of the Pharmacovigilance Program of India (PvPI) in 2010 • Setting up ADR monitoring centres in different parts of India 	None reported	None reported	None reported
12. Mehta et al., (58). 2014	Mixed	To outline findings and recommendations of a national	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a national PV plan underpinned by five key principles: 	None reported	None reported	None reported

South Africa		pharmacovigilance workshop held in August 2012 in South Africa.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory, programmatic and institutional PV incorporated into a cohesive national system • The national PV system should contribute to treatment policy decision-making and improved patient care • The national PV system should incorporate both passive and active surveillance methods and leverage successes • Investment in capacity building and training in PV and pharmacoepidemiology • Feedback and communication to stakeholders 			
13. The National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (59), 2019 Nigeria	Mixed	Presentation of the National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) Strategic Plan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic focus 3: Safety and Quality of Regulated Products – to strengthen the Platform for Easy Reporting of Adverse Events and Timely Resolution 	None reported	None reported	None reported
14. National Drug Authority Uganda (60), 2020	Mixed	To provide a strategy to guide PV activities for the period 2018 to 2022.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance technical capacity at all levels involved in PV to improve safety data management and signal detection. • Strengthen existing reporting systems through implementation of smart safety surveillance initiatives. • Ensure that existing laws, regulations and guidelines comprehensively cover all areas of drug regulation including marketing authorisation holders. • Enhance information exchange between all PV stakeholders, both national and international, and facilitate collaboration through harmonisation of activities. 	None reported	None reported	None reported
15. Federal Ministry of Health Nigeria,	Mixed	To provide a framework and holistic approach for the	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setting up of PV structures 	None reported	None reported	None reported

(61), 2020 Nigeria		implementation of the national PV policy in all tiers of the healthcare system.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishing procedures to achieve defined outcomes and impacts by key PV partners Define key performance indicators to measure performance and outputs 			
16. Nguyen et al., (62), 2018 Vietnam	Mixed	To provide an overall picture of the Vietnamese PV system since the establishment of the National Drug Information and Adverse Drug Reaction Monitoring Centre (NDIADRM) and describe lessons learnt in a resource-limited country when dealing with PV issues.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NDIADRM established in 2009 Between 2010 and 2015, the Ministry of Health issued a number of legal documents related to PV Linkages between PV activities and targeted PHPs have been established and improved over time Education of HCP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Functional safety surveillance system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variation in the quality and quantity of reports between regions, hospitals, and HCP Limited Communication, Training, and Information Sharing Divisions Between Activities Coordinating Public Health Lack of Involvement from Private Drug Retailers, Customers, and Public Media 	None reported
17. Nzolo et al., (63), 2019 DRC	Mixed	To share the experience of the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) in developing its own PV System and to put its best practices and bottlenecks into a broader perspective.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5-day training of PV focal points, sensitization of HCP, establishment and training of NECs Establishing reporting and feedback mechanism Supervision visits Enhanced spontaneous reporting at the community level Active PV (cohort event monitoring) for specific drugs implemented 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creation of national PV centre Implementation of PV at Kinshasa university Signal detection activities initiated in DRC Collaboration established between PV stakeholders VigiFlow™ installed and functional PV included in curriculum of medicine, pharmacy, and dentistry schools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politics issues around location of national PV centre and conflict of interest between stakeholders Lack of funding Lack of comprehensive and validated guidelines for PV activities Poor response from some stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved stakeholder collaboration at all levels essential to incorporate PV into the national health system
18. PhArmacoVigilance Africa, (64), 2021 LMIC	Mixed	To provide the critical steps and actions that should be put in place in a proactive and well-coordinated manner in order to effectively implement a national pharmacovigilance policy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholders Engagement Statutory Endorsement Institutionalization of the Pharmacovigilance Policy Addressing the Roles and Responsibilities of Stakeholders Secure funding" 	None reported	None reported	None reported

19. Sydykov et al., (65), 2016 Republic of Kazakhstan	Mixed	To describe the key stages in the development of pharmacovigilance in the Republic of Kazakhstan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of the national PV centre in 2002 • 2005 to 2008 - development of the system of ADR monitor • Establish regulatory framework for public PV system • 2009 improving and harmonizing the regulatory documents in drug safety control. 	None reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low activity of manufacturers on reporting of ADRs • Underreporting by HCP • Poor understanding and involvement of patients and consumers • Lack of an integrated information system for all participants in the monitoring of ADR 	None reported
20. Tanani et al., (66), 2017 Morocco	Mixed	To demonstrate the various steps of successful model of integrating PV in Moroccan Tuberculosis Control Program (PV-MTCP).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designation of national coordinator of PV • New technical committee on PV established • Collection of reports and feed back to reporters • Electronic recording of ADR reports • Data processing and signal management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant increase in number of ADR reports (3.6 to 37.4 cases/month) after integration of the PV programme 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient files for those who have did not develop ADRs were unavailable to estimate the incidence of ADRs and risk factors 	None reported
21. For Research on Diseases of Poverty, (67), 2022 Malawi	Mixed	To introduce innovative techniques to enhance reporting of adverse drug reactions and adverse events following immunization.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A nationwide media campaign to raise awareness of the public and enhance reporting of suspected ADRs • Extensive cascade training targeting district-level PV focal points • Measure the impact of the training programme, via a Knowledge, Attitude and Practice survey • Developed a USSD (Unstructured Supplementary Service Data) platform for reporting ADRs and AEFI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2.8 fold increase in the rate of ADR detection and 1.8 fold increase in ADR reporting rate • Significant increase in ADR reports from 15 to 297 six months after the training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of reporting forms, delay in transferring reports and lack of feedback 	None reported
22. Tanzania Medicines and Medical Devices Authority, (68), 2021 Tanzania	Mixed	To develop a roadmap to outline activities to be undertaken to overcome gaps and challenges identified during the baseline situational analysis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve the efficiency and functioning of regulatory and organizational structures of PV activities • Define and clarify the roles and responsibilities for all PV stakeholders 	None reported	None reported	None reported

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the effectiveness of active (sentinel) surveillance of ADRs • Improve connectivity of databases and use of PV tools for event detection, reporting, analysis and dissemination • Increase resources to sufficiently exercise safety -monitoring • Improve PV-relevant skills and competencies at various levels • Improve monitoring and evaluation of the performance of the PV system • Enhance national, regional and international initiatives and networking in relation to PV skills, knowledge and better resource mobilization and utilization 			
23. World Health Organization (69), 2018 Malawi, Ghana, Kenya	Mixed	To describe PV readiness indicators of vaccine PV in preparation for vaccine introduction.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV harmonization and capacity-building • Focused refresher training programmes and root cause analysis • Development of tools, guidelines, job aids • Establishment and training of national safety committees • Shared line-lists, printing and distribution of reporting tools and surveillance manual 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vaccine safety surveillance systems strengthened • Increase reporting of AEFI 	None reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The baseline surveillance systems established in these countries could be used for detecting AESI associated with other vaccine introductions, such as for COVID-19
24. World Health Organization (70), 2017 Global	Mixed	To propose a strategy to strengthen PV capacity in LMICs and, in the long-term, establish end-to end safety surveillance of products from their clinical development to the post market stages.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt a stepwise approach with an initial pilot for three new products (two medicines and one vaccine) • Leverage available resources from partners • Develop integrated plans that include key marketing authorization holders • Develop a holistic plan for PV • Collaboration with other ongoing initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant increase in ADR reporting rates • Increased quality of reports • Increased capacity for signal detection and increased capacity to assess risk management 	None reported	None reported

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build PV infrastructure progressively, moving from minimum to mid-range and advanced capacity." 			
25. World Health Organization (71), 2021 Global	Mixed	The Global Vaccine Safety Blueprint (GVSB) provides strategies to establish systems that optimize the monitoring of vaccine safety profiles throughout their life-cycle; moving from a minimal and enhanced capacity concept to maturity levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To help LMICs to implement at least minimal capacity for vaccine safety activities • To enhance capacity for vaccine safety assessment in countries that introduce newly-developed vaccines • To establish a global vaccine safety support structure." 	None reported	None reported	None reported

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